

METHODOLOGY FOR FORMATION OF LANGUAGE LEARNING MOTIVES IN EDUCATORS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract. *In this article, views on the formation of motives for language learning in children of pre-school educational organizations, on increasing children's interest in language through modern technologies in language learning are considered. Moreover, we are analyzed language learning methods.*

Keywords: *language, motive, children, technology, organization, foreign language, event.*

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired in the natural environment, that is, in the family, among the public or in an organized manner. Knowledge of language phenomena is taught theoretically. Languages in our times, when international relations are on the rise knowledge, especially multilingualism, is of great importance. In our country students usually learn three languages. These languages are specially managed by names. These are: mother tongue, second language, and foreign language. Mother tongue is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. Second when talking about language, it means brothers and sisters of other nationalities, it is considered as the language of neighbors.

The process of learning and teaching a language is considered a complex phenomenon, and age has always been of great importance in this process. The reason is that it is easier to learn a language at an early age. The process of language learning in children is well consolidated in memory.

Nowadays, the demand for language learning is increasing. When children learn a language from the age of 3, it is a very convenient time for them: children of this age differ in terms of memory and speech. The younger the child, the less vocabulary he has and the greater the need for pronunciation.

There are different methods of teaching language to children. For example, if we communicate in a foreign language on the street, at school or at home in our normal daily life, we think that it will be good for the child, but it is more effective for older children. Because in many cases, the child may lose interest in learning this language in such a situation.

The main goals of teaching a foreign language to preschool children are:

- formation of children's basic communication skills in a foreign language;
- the ability to use a foreign language to achieve one's goals, to express one's thoughts and feelings in life communication;
- creating a positive attitude to further study of foreign languages;
- to arouse interest in the life and culture of other countries.

School practice shows that studying the group of students should be organized taking into account their interests, aspirations and desires, or providing the mastery of educational materials with the purposeful orientation of the educational and cognitive activities of students. It is known

that in order to organize lessons and ensure the activity of students during the lesson, it is necessary to first take into account the educational motivations of students or to form their motivations for science. The main reason for this is that the students' educational and cognitive motives, motives in general form the basis of activity. Motives are the main driving force of the didactic process. Learning motivational motives, using them correctly and being able to direct them correctly determine the main essence of the content of pedagogical activity. It is important to form motivations for language learning in children.

According to Stefan Krashen, the learner must first have a need to learn the language, or an environmental requirement, in such a situation, a language learner's personal need for natural exchange of information regarding obligations encourages speaking in the language. How a young language learner learns his mother tongue, in the same way he tries to speak a foreign language, that is, the need to communicate with parents and relatives encourages. By learning the language in this way, speaking skills are developed naturally. But for those who learned the language in this way, the skills of written speech are not well developed.

Preschool age is especially favorable for starting to learn a foreign language. Children of this age are distinguished by their sensitivity to language phenomena, they are interested in understanding their speech experiences, the "secrets" of language.

The methodology of conducting direct educational activities should be built taking into account the age and individual characteristics of the structure of children's language skills and should be directed to their development. Communication in a foreign language should be motivational and directed. It is necessary to create a positive psychological attitude towards a foreign language in a child, and the way to create such a positive motivation is to play. The game is both a form of organization and a method of conducting lessons in which children gather a certain amount of English vocabulary, learn many poems, songs, count rhymes, etc. This form of conducting lessons creates favorable conditions for mastering language skills and speaking skills. The ability to rely on game activity allows you to give a natural impetus to speech in a foreign language, to make even the simplest phrases interesting and meaningful. Playing in the teaching of a foreign language does not contradict the educational activity, but is organically connected with it. "The game is a specially organized activity, in which the child's emotional feelings and mental abilities are mobilized, how to act when making a decision, how to express an opinion, how to achieve success, etc. accelerates the child's thinking ability. Children begin to learn a foreign language in a way that they did not even think about".

The main goals of modern education are to increase the interest of students and children through the use of modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process. Therefore, if innovative methods are used in language learning with children of preschool educational organizations, children's interest in language will increase.

In addition, the educator uses objects in the process of teaching to form motivations for language learning. For example, when teaching related words, you first show the object to the child and encourage him to say it, the students pronounce the words, and repeat the new word again using the pictures on the cards to reinforce the word they said. In the teaching of words, teachers can determine the content of the text, and in order to attract the attention of students, the educator can draw their picture on the board by pronouncing the words together with them.

Therefore, currently in China, a teacher is required to have drawing skills. This not only reduces the difficulty of teaching, but also helps students to gradually consolidate the knowledge

they have learned. In order for students to feel their progress in the process of learning the English language, it is necessary to have a perfect approach to each educational activity. That is the only way children are motivated to learn. As Chinese kindergarten-age children are now more receptive to new knowledge, the curriculum in kindergartens has been intensified accordingly.

Furthermore, technologies for the formation of motivation for language learning include, for example, a marker board, videos for learning different languages on TV, songs for hearing in audio form.

Watching cartoons is a very effective way to learn a foreign language. There are even some cartoons designed to help children learn a foreign language. In this type of shows, instead of leaving children in front of the TV, it is recommended to bring the child into the conversation process through cartoons. This idea is found in interactive educational cartoons and it helps to improve children's listening and pronunciation skills. You can find such TV shows on Netflix. It has many TV shows for kids and it gives you the option to add subtitles and switch languages.

Age is very important in language learning. Therefore, taking into account the children's age, language learning methods suitable for their psychology are developed. During the teaching of a foreign language to children from 3 to 6-7 years of age, the duration of training is also important. Classes are usually 20-45 minutes long. Otherwise, children will be mentally tired and bored, and their interest in learning something new may fade. Because of this, it is appropriate to use the most interesting and colorful methods in teaching English to children. Another such method is to explain a topic through songs with the help of hand movements. For example, simply teaching the topic of family in English is ineffective. On the contrary, memorizing with hand movements in the style of a song is more effective. Chances of keeping children in memory will increase.

In conclusion, childhood is a period of rapid development in personality formation, and this period is a complex period. Language learning is one of the most important issues today. When teaching children, a foreign language, it is necessary to take into account their age, opportunities and potential. Also, it is necessary to teach children a foreign language not as a simple lesson or as an obligation, but as an interesting activity, using various effective and colorful methods. Only then it is possible to develop a strong desire and interest in children. Modern methods of language teaching are important for children to choose a future profession and become a perfect person.

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